

CHECKING TECHNOLOGY OF VOCABULARY BANK IN PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN WITH UNDEVELOPED SPEECH

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Abstract. *This article presents the methodology and results of checking vocabulary in preschool children with underdeveloped speech.*

Keywords: *speech, disability, deficiency, motivational-need sphere.*

Introduction. In the first years of a child's life, he changes from the appearance of a helpless person to a social, mobile and active person. It is during early childhood that the process of mastering important components of human experience takes place, these processes are the foundation of the next stages of development: mental activity, emotions, the basis of the motivational-need sphere develops, independent walking and speech are prepared. The lack of contact with the environment during this period has a negative impact on the future mental activity of the child. According to L.O. Badalyan, "primary learning is formed during this period, that is, an ensemble of neurons is formed that will help in mastering somewhat complex types of activities in the future"[1].

The years 2022-20226 will go down in the history of our country with the ambitious goals of establishing the "New Uzbekistan" society and laying the foundations of the "Third Renaissance". The precision, strategic importance and scope of the implemented reforms and initiatives are recognized not only by local but also by international experts. In the context of reforms, the attention paid to education and science deserves special recognition. During the next five years, a number of Presidential decrees and decisions were adopted to fundamentally improve all levels of education. These received documents are distinguished by their closeness to life from a practical point of view. The main goal of all reforms in the field of education is to educate spiritually well-developed people, to implement them in accordance with the needs of the times based on the improvement of the education system.

In modern speech therapy, there is a large amount of research material on the problem of children with underdeveloped speech of preschool age. Following the studies [1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10, etc.], which based the consideration of speech disorders from the point of view of systemic-symptomatic analysis, other researchers during the last 10-15 years have also studied all components of the speech system. Research continues to address impairments and enable speech-impaired children to speak independently.

Methods (research methods): The purpose of conducting an emphatic experiment aimed at researching the vocabulary of children with underdeveloped speech is to describe the state of active and passive vocabulary of children and its use in children's speech activity, a methodology was developed. A total of 120 speech-impaired children participated in the experiment.

In the course of the stress experiment, given to children with underdeveloped speech and in accordance with the tasks aimed at determining the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of children's vocabulary, children were asked about five topics ("Toys", "Transport", "Pets", "Clothes", "Shoes") four tasks were offered.

Task 1. Classification of concepts. Material: 30 pictures of pets, clothes, shoes, toys, fruits, vegetables, vehicles. For each topic, the teacher names the concept represented by a group of pictures and asks the child being tested to give its full definition and then select the corresponding pictures. For example, what animals are pets? Choose pictures of pets. In each task, the number of correctly selected pictures is counted, each correct answer is evaluated with 1 point. 2 points are awarded for the wrong picture. The highest score is 30 points.

Task 2. Choosing antonyms. It is held in the form of a game "Tell the opposite". The child is invited to play with words: he must choose a word that has the opposite meaning to the spoken word. A total of 10 words are required (young-old, happy-sad, thin-fat, tall-short, cowardly-bold, close-far, laugh-cry, run-shut up, talk-keep silent). 1 point is given for each correct answer, 0 points are given if the meaning of the selected word is not an antonym of the given word. The highest score is 10 points.

Task 3. Choosing synonyms. It is played in the form of the game "What is another name". The child is invited to find a word close in meaning to the spoken word. A total of 10 words are given (for example, happy, old, big, coward, good, beautiful, leaf, laugh, cry, run). Here too, each correct answer is evaluated with 1 point, and each incorrect answer with 0 points. A child with 10 points gets the highest grade.

Task 4. Choice of identifiers. Played as a word game. The child is invited to find as many qualifiers as possible to the spoken word. A total of 5 words are offered (eg ball, tree, dog, apple, man). In this, the teacher-speech therapist will ask the child relevant questions. (For example, a tree. What is it like? What can it look like? What color is it? etc.). A child who finds more than three words that are semantically similar to the said word is given 2 points for each correct answer, and a child who finds less than 3 words is given 1 point. An answer where the found word does not match the semantic field of the suggested word is scored with 0 points.

After completing four tasks aimed at determining the vocabulary of speech-impaired children, a summative assessment is made. The highest score is 60 points, indicating a high level. A score of 35-50 indicates an average level of the child's vocabulary development, and a score of less than 35 indicates a low level.

The obtained data made it possible to determine the comparative ability of children to use certain elements of acquired lexicon in their speech. The quantitative results of children's speech showed the extent to which their speech, especially their lexicon, has developed. The given tasks made it possible to assess children's skills in using different vocabulary in their speech. During the experiment, children were asked to interpret the meanings of words. Quantitative analysis of children's responses allowed to determine which lexical subject words children had more difficulty in interpreting word meanings. When evaluating quality indicators, we focused on the nature of errors made by children, the reasons for their occurrence, and the extent to which they understand the meaning of each word. In the qualitative analysis, children's ability to choose synonyms and antonyms for the proposed words, and to evaluate the character and structure of semantic relations between words were taken into account.

The following indicators are based on the evaluations obtained during the analysis of the results: the size of the active vocabulary; giving the exact ratio of the word to the proposed picture; to be able to determine the categories of words denoting the subject according to the semantic sign; the ability to distinguish words denoting actions and symbols and to choose antonyms based on the proposed pictures; the ability to distinguish and describe the seasons. Objects, events and their

signs, pictures representing their actions were selected for control-experimental tasks according to the thematic principle. During the work with the pictures, questions were asked to help determine the children's vocabulary in terms of noun, adjective and verb groups. When identifying passive words related to nouns in the children's lexicon, they were offered a total of 158 pictures selected on the basis of the program material by topic: 43 pictures on the topic "Transport", 46 pictures on the topic "Pets", 50 pictures on the topic "clothing", "Shoes" 19 pictures on the topic. When performing the task, the children had to choose the pictures in a sequence offered by the experimenter.

Results (research results): One of the characteristics of the lexicon of children with underdeveloped speech is the difference in the size of their active and passive vocabulary. Preschool children whose speech is not fully developed do not understand the meaning of many words, the size of their passive vocabulary does not correspond to their youth. It is difficult to choose words in expressive speech, to find the right word from the vocabulary. Even six-year-old children, whose speech is not fully developed, do not have the ability to generalize: they can name fish, colors, birds, domestic and wild animals, professions, body parts, tools, etc. They don't know many words.

One of the distinctive features of the lexicon of children with speech impairment is that they cannot use words for a specific purpose. This is expressed in verbal paraphasias. Sometimes children use words only in certain situations. Thus, understanding the meaning of the word and using it depends on the situation.

During the experiment, the number of correctly identified pictures and the number of incorrectly found pictures were determined. The number of children who refused to answer the questions on the topic "Transport" turned out to be the highest (69.0% - incorrect answers, 17.1% - those who refused to answer). 23.8% of children answered correctly when completing the topic "Pets", which was the highest number of correct answers given for this topic.

The main reason for the errors observed in the responses of preschool children with speech impairment is the lack of vocabulary. This is expressed in the poverty and lack of differentiation of the vocabulary, in the lack of words belonging to the verb group, in the replacement of words according to the similarity of objects, in the incorrect use of individual words or in complete ignorance, in the confusion of words according to the relationship of type and variety. Three groups of children were identified as a result of the study of the vocabulary of pre-school children whose speech is not fully developed.

In the first group of preschool children with speech deficiency (11.0%), the means of speech communication are completely absent, while gestural communication is relatively preserved. The active vocabulary of such children consists of a very small number of household imitation words and 2-3 articulatory sounds, which are vaguely pronounced. Sound imitations are pronounced depending on the situation and are distinguished by their uniqueness, the vocabulary of such children can be evaluated as one-word sentences.

The vocabulary of children belonging to the second group (24.0%) is limited both quantitatively and qualitatively. They have no idea about the name, color, signs, dimensions, shape of the objects, and accordingly, the words expressing these concepts have not taken place in their vocabulary. There are also no general words in their vocabulary, words are often interchanged. Passive vocabulary is much more than active vocabulary. Children show vegetables, fruits, animals, objects that express movement, but they cannot say the quality of objects. Children

belonging to this group distinguish singular and plural numbers. However, their understanding of speech remains limited, and they struggle to answer questions or respond with gestures.

When examining the level of speech development of children belonging to the third group (65.0%), it became clear that they misunderstand the meanings of many words in their vocabulary. The nominative and predicative lexicon is much larger in number than the group of words denoting the quality, sign, and action of objects. There are cases of using words interchangeably: calling a general concept by its part ("snow" instead of "winter", "car" instead of "transport", etc.). Agrammatisms, phonetic and structural disorders were observed in children's speech.

Discussions. Thus, studies have shown that the vocabulary of preschool children with speech impairment is formed very slowly and uniquely. The slow development of speech, difficulties in acquiring vocabulary, combined with difficulties in understanding self-directed speech, limit the child's speech communication with peers and adults, hinder the child's full activity for this, long-term special speech therapy is required.

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